

A 66Gbps/5.5W RISC-V Many-Core Cluster for 5G+ Software-Defined Radio Uplinks

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Abstract—Following the scale-up of New Radio complexity in 5G and beyond, the physical layer’s computing load on base stations is increasing under a strictly constrained latency and power budget: base stations must process > 20 Gbps uplink wireless data rate on the fly, in < 10 W. At the same time, the programmability and reconfigurability of base station components is a key requirement: it reduces the time and cost of new networks’ deployment, it lowers the acceptance threshold for industry players to enter the market, it ensures return on investments in a fast-paced evolution of standards. In this paper, we present the design of a many-core cluster for 5G and beyond base station processing. Our design features 1024, streamlined RISC-V cores with domain-specific floating-point extensions, and 4 MiB shared memory. It provides the necessary computational capabilities for software-defined processing of the lower physical layer of 5G physical uplink shared channel (PUSCH), satisfying high-end throughput requirements (66 Gbps for a Transition Time Interval (TTI), 9.4-302 Gbps depending on the processing stage). The throughput metrics for the implemented functions are 10 times higher than in state-of-the-art application-specific instruction processors. The energy efficiency on key New Radio kernels (2-41 Gbps/W), measured at 800 MHz, 25°C, 0.8 V, on a placed and routed instance in 12nm CMOS technology, is competitive with state-of-the-art architectures. The PUSCH processing runs end-to-end on a single cluster in 1.7 ms, at < 6 W average power consumption, achieving 12 Gbps/W.

Index Terms—6G, Software-Defined Radio, Many-Core, RISC-V, ASIC.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 5th generation (5G) wireless system standard has been a key enabler for high data rate, low latency, and ultra-reliable mobile services. It was introduced in 2017 by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Release-15 [1], and it enabled numerous applications: augmented reality, internet of things, device-to-device and vehicles to everything communications, remote healthcare, machine-to-machine and drone communications [2], [3]. Application studies expect that transitioning to 6th generation (6G) will bring further advancements, including telepresence, autonomous driving vehicles, indoor and outdoor wireless positioning&sensing [4]–[6]. The total global mobile data traffic, reached 145 EB/month at the end of 2023 and is projected to grow by 3.5 \times , touching the threshold of 466 EB/month in 2029 [7].

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As a consequence of this staggering data volume, computing challenges are rapidly rising at the edge nodes of the telecommunication infrastructure. The key requirements for 5G and 6G networks mandate that the peak uplink data rate will grow from 20 Gbps to 1 Tbps, and the round trip latency will decrease, from 1 ms to 0.1 ms. There will be 10 \times more devices per unit area (from 10⁶dev/km² to 10⁷dev/km²), and the spectrum usage will extend from below 6 GHz up to the sub-THz frequency bands [5], [6], [8]. Therefore, extremely high-performance digital signal processing (DSP) hardware must be developed to sustain huge data rates at an acceptable throughput. Optimizations will be focused on the remote units (RUs) of radio access networks (RANs) because the up-link and down-link protocols implemented in the RUs directly affect the user equipments (UEs) experienced latency and require the fast consumption of data on the flight [9].

Nowadays, digital processing in 5G base stations (BSs), i.e. the digital part of gNodeB (gNB) processing, is performed on heterogeneous platforms. General-purpose programmable cores orchestrate the user data streams, while different application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) accelerators process the signal [10]. Looking forward, in the competitive landscape of a fast-paced evolution telecommunication standard, resorting to fully programmable software-defined BSs is a highly desirable paradigm shift. First, the software-defined paradigm [11], [12], allows reducing the time to market in the deployment of new telecommunications standards, by softwarizing the blocks of the signal chain that can most rapidly evolve and by opening the way for differentiation opportunities and value-added functions. Many industry players adapted to this trend, offering programmable hardware BS components and software libraries tailored for them [13], [14]. Second, a software-defined approach helps to lower startup costs, increasing productivity and market growth. Third, it reduces the need to replace components in an installed BS, while making sure it can keep up with the evolving standard. The latter is a key economic motivation for companies to move towards softwarization of their processing: most of the vendors estimate the return on investments (ROI) over wireless networks deployment to 5-10 years [15], but telecommunication protocols evolved faster. Between 2015 and 2025 they moved from long-term evolution (LTE), to 4th generation (4G), then to 5G, and finally to 6G.

Energy efficiency is the key metric to trade off with programmability in software-defined gNB processing. Upper bounds on power consumption emerged upon pushing the physical layer (PHY) processing to the RUs edge network

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nodes, to improve the quality of service: nowadays, the RUs contribute to 40% of total RAN power consumption [16]. According to a survey on 4G networks [17] up to 90% of the 1-2 kW consumed by a 5G BS with 64 transceivers [18] is dissipated in essential operational costs (power amplifiers, power supply, and air conditioning). With only 100 W left for analog and digital signal processing, we can assume 10 W power consumption per BS component. Therefore, beyond 5G processors require > 2 Gbps/W energy efficiency.

In this paper, we move from the general architectural template of TeraPool [19], a fully programmable 1024-core cluster, and we enhance and develop it for gNB signal processing, in particular for the lower-PHY of the 5G-Physical Uplink Shared Channel (PUSCH) channel. Our many-core design is fundamentally different from legacy gNB processing solutions based on inflexible DSP accelerators [20]–[25]. Our design matches the requirements of software-defined wireless processing: each core of the compute fabric can be individually programmed. Our solution also addresses the challenges created by programmable clusters with few big cores, which would suffer from work imbalance and data movement overhead [26]–[29]. We propose instead an architecture with hundreds of small, energy-efficient cores that access shared data memory in parallel. With this architecture, we enable true single-program multiple-data (SPMD) on a large workload generated by the lower-PHY PUSCH processing.

The micro-architecture of our cores is based on the RISC-V open instruction set architecture (ISA). We open-sourced our register transfer level (RTL) code, toolchains, and software¹, promoting hardware-software co-design, in line with the software-defined approach.

This work represents a significant extension of our previous exploration on the efficient parallelization of 5G-PHY micro-kernels on many-core clusters [30]. The key contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- 1) We design extensions for the RISC-V cores to support floating-point (FP) computation at low hardware overhead (Zfxn [31]), augmented with domain-specific instructions to address the most common formats and precisions of telecommunication data (fixed-point or FP complex 16 b real, 16 b imaginary).
- 2) We implement software-defined end-to-end processing for the lower-PHY of 5G PUSCH (i.e. demodulation, beamforming, channel estimation, and signal detection), one of the most demanding tasks of the PHY at the BS. We schedule the processing steps to promote data reuse in the level-one (L1) memory, reducing the runtime of 12% compared to loading all operands and storing all outputs in level-two (L2) memory for each step.
- 3) We place and route our design in a 12 nm FinFET technology, and measure its throughput and energy efficiency at 800 MHz, 25°C, 0.8 V, in a high-load use case. We compare our results with state-of-the-art (SoTA) solutions for gNB signal processing.

We estimate average power consumption of < 6 W and a total latency of 2.6 ms (fixed-point) and 1.7 ms (FP plus

domain-specific extensions) for the execution of the addressed PUSCH functions, at 12 Gbps/W per symbol, which is highly competitive with all the SoTA solutions for which we could gather performance, power and efficiency data.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the architecture and programming model of the many-core cluster developed to sustain the high throughput requirements of beyond 5G workloads, focusing on the processing cores architecture and ISA and the hierarchical core-to-memory interconnect. Section III describes: III-A the uplink workload selected to benchmark the performance of the cluster; III-B the implementation of 5G parallel micro-kernels on the cluster, and III-C their performance; III-D the full PUSCH pipeline execution. Section IV presents the physical implementation and power-performance-area (PPA) of our many-core cluster on software-defined lower-PHY workloads, introducing a comparison on energy efficiency with SoTA application-specific instruction processors (ASIPs) and ASIC in Section V. Section VI concludes the paper.

II. TERAPOL FOR SOFTWARE-DEFINED PHYSICAL LAYER: ARCHITECTURE & PROGRAMMING MODEL

We address the low latency and high throughput of 5G New Radio (NR), exploiting the performance and scalability of TeraPool [19]. This large cluster features 1024 processing cores, each supporting the RV32IMAF ISA, and a shared multi-banked L1 scratchpad. This section details the micro-architecture of the cores and the ISA extensions introduced for software-defined PHY workloads. We describe TeraPool’s shared memory interconnect, focusing on the advantages offered in simplifying the programming model and reducing data transfers. Finally, we give details of the SPMD programming model adopted for software-defined PHY kernels.

A. Core-Complex: Physical Layer Specific Extensions

The TeraPool core-complex, represented in Figure 1, is based on the *Snitch* single-stage, single-issue lightweight core [32]. The core decodes and executes instructions in the RV32I base ISA in one cycle, it offloads multi-cycle instructions to specialized functional units. *Snitch* book-keeps the dependencies of offloaded instructions in a scoreboard and proceeds in the program flow. As a result, their additional latency is hidden as long as they do not have data dependencies². The *Snitch* core-complex in TeraPool includes an integer processing unit (IPU), implementing integer multiplication and division, and the *Xpulpim* extensions. The latter provide single-instruction multiple-data (SIMD) shuffling, packing, and unpacking of half types and are useful to manipulate complex 16 b data, typical in classical radio signal processing.

For PUSCH processing and more in general for 5G (and beyond) software-defined PHY-processing, we also included 32 b and 16 b FP support. In gNB workloads, FP numbers

²*Snitch* can keep fetching and executing new instructions if their input operands do not depend on operands of previously issued and not yet completed instructions.

¹<https://github.com/pulp-platform/mempool>

Fig. 1. Snitch core with offload ports to the IPU, FP-SS, and shared division and square-root functional units. According to Zfinx specifications, the FP operands are in the integer RF.

Fig. 2. The modular FPU circuit has four functional slices. The wDotp unit is extended to perform one-cycle complex wDotp.

help code development: they reduce the full-scale range adjustments, required to combine processing steps and to fine-tune the application if the transmission context changes. They also help to keep high numerical precision for the inversion of large matrices, which is a common operation for Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) antenna systems [33].

To maximize the compute units' area-efficiency, we support the *Zfinx* and *Zhinx* standard extensions [31]. They implement the same FP 32b and 16b instructions as in the *F* and *Zfh* extensions, but use only the 32 registers available in the base core (also used for integer operations), eliminating the area overhead of a FP-register file (RF) and dedicated FP load&stores. The floating point sub-system (FP-SS) shares the same port of the IPU and includes a decoding stage and the configurable floating point unit (FPU) *fpnew* module [34] in Figure 2. This component groups and implements FP extensions in four slices: addition&multiplication, comparison, cast, and dot-product.

To further improve the cores' performance on 5G kernels we configure the FPU for SIMD 16b and widening dot-product (w-Dotp) [35] support. We exploit the w-Dotp 16b to 32b slice of the FPU to implement FP arithmetic on 32b complex data types (16b real, 16b imaginary part). We instantiate one w-Dotp slice for the real part and one for the imaginary. The 16b input and output operands are combined as in Figure 1.

The receiving step of a 5G gNB often requires matrix-

inversions [36]. FP division and square-root instructions are often used to implement these operators. Four cores share the same division and square-root unit with a round-robin policy to reduce the area overhead of these extensions, which are typically less frequently used than the basic FP operators.

Each core complex has a private load&store unit (LSU). Loads, stores, and atomic instructions support are discussed in the next subsection, alongside the cluster L1 interconnect.

B. Cluster Interconnect

In TeraPool, the L1 memory hierarchy is a multi-banked scratchpad, fully shared between 1024 processors. This architecture can be programmed with a streamlined SPMD approach, where all the cores have low latency access to data structures in L1 memory, that they process in parallel. However, routing congestion and the related effort in floorplanning, placement, and routing make an all-to-all flat crossbar (X-BAR) interconnect between the cores and the scratchpad banks not physically feasible, even for smaller configurations than TeraPool's [37]. To ensure physical feasibility, the cores are partitioned into 4 hierarchical levels. The cross-hierarchy memory access paths are shared by groups of cores with round-robin arbitration. Pipeline cuts are introduced on these paths to achieve near-GHz frequency targets, resulting in a non-uniform memory access (NUMA) latency shared-L1 architecture [19]. There is a large configuration space in this 4-level interconnect hierarchy. For software-defined processing of the lower-PHY, we select the most promising configuration for energy-efficiency [19]. In a low load traffic condition, any core in the cluster accesses any bank in less than 9-cycles.

The *Tile* in Figure 3a is the *1st* implementation hierarchy. It contains 8 core complexes, 2 shared division and square-root FP units, 4 KiB of shared instruction cache (I\$), and 32 KiB of scratchpad memory, divided into 32 banks, namely the Tightly-Coupled Data Memory (TCDM). The cores' LSUs access the banks in 1-cycle through a local X-BAR built with a logarithmic number of stages. A reservation table per bank handles atomic load&stores. Cores can hide TeraPool's NUMA interconnect latency by issuing up to 8 outstanding transactions. Issued load&stores are tracked by keeping their metadata in a transaction table. Unless a read after write (RAW) dependency occurs, load&stores are non-blocking for the next instruction execution.

Figure 3b represents the hierarchical connections of Tiles that we adopted for software-defined lower-PHY applications. The *2nd* implementation hierarchy is a *SubGroup*, with 8 Tiles. All cores in a Tile have a shared request-response port to an 8×8 TCDM X-BAR, addressing the memory of other Tiles in the SubGroup. The *3rd* implementation hierarchy is a *Group*, with 4 SubGroups. In a Group, the Tiles of a SubGroup access the TCDM of Tiles in other SubGroups via a shared request-response port, connected to one 8×8 TCDM X-BAR per SubGroup. The *4th* level of the hierarchy is a *Cluster*, with 4 Groups. The 32 Tiles in a Group access the TCDM of Tiles in other Groups via 32×32 TCDM X-BARs, and one shared request-response port per Group in each Tile.

As described in [37], an AXI interconnect is also instantiated in each hierarchical level. The AXI interconnect has three

Fig. 3. a) The TeraPool Tile, with 8 Snitch core-complexes and 2 shared division and square-root FP units. The local Req/Resp X-BAR gives 1 cycle access to the shared TCDM, 7 remote Req/Resp master, and slave ports connect to other hierarchical levels. b) The connections between TeraPool Tiles (T0-7 for each SubGroup) and SubGroups (SG0-3) in a Group.

main functions. First, it connects the cores to the L2 memory, the cluster peripherals, and a cluster-shared direct memory access (DMA) engine. Second, it allows I\$ refill. The cores and the I\$ share the same AXI port at the Tile level. Third, it carries streamlined DMA transfers between the L2 and the shared-L1 scratchpad banks. A DMA frontend is individually programmed by each core through reads and writes on the AXI interconnect. Data transfers are initiated by the frontend. They run over the AXI interconnect and they are redistributed to banks by a DMA backend in each SubGroup. The DMA backend and the Tiles' AXI requests and responses share the same 512b wide port at the SubGroup level. Therefore, the whole cluster has a 1024B/cycle AXI link to L2 memory, containing both instructions and data.

C. SPMD Programming Model for Software-Defined PHY

The big workloads of 5G lower-PHY are parallelized over the many cores of the cluster, using a fork-join programming model. By default, all the cores execute the program in parallel. By runtime calls, each core reads its private ID from a status-register. The programmer can use this ID to index conditional branches and loops, distributing the workload between cores. At the end of the assigned parallel task, cores synchronize and enter a new parallel task. Adopting the same SPMD paradigm used for small TCDM clusters of 4 to 16 cores has the advantage of simplifying the programming model, but it could incur synchronization overheads. The cluster's C-runtime includes two main synchronization primitives [38]. In the *linear barrier*, cores atomically write a shared synchronization variable and go in a wait for interrupt (WFI) state; the last core fetching from the shared memory location resets the variable and wakes up all the others. The *logarithmic barrier* implements a synchronization tree: first, the cores synchronize in groups by atomic writes to multiple locations, then the last core in each group continues to the next level of the tree, where the same pattern repeats. The core passing through all the synchronization levels wakes up the cluster. The wake-up is centrally handled, via a shared wake-up register and hardwired wake-up trigger connections to each core. The wake-up triggers to each core can be asserted with a Tile granularity, implementing *partial synchronization* between subsets of cores in the cluster [38].

We developed an open-source library of wireless DSP kernels deeply optimized for our many-core architecture. The kernels are written in C and compiled with *LLVM 12.0*. We modified the compiler backend to support the added PHY-processing ISA extensions. For the design of kernels, we adopt a bare-metal approach. We parallelize loops assigning independent time iterations or input data portions to different cores, according to their unique ID. Kernels can be run standalone, using the compute fabric as a programmable accelerator, or stitched together, to set up an in-line processing pipeline. This is further clarified in Section III-B and Section III-D.

III. PUSCH COMPUTATION

This section describes PUSCH, one of the most computing-intensive channel of the 5G uplink. We detail the parallelization scheme adopted to implement the PUSCH addressed functions and present an execution of the whole processing chain, up to the minimum mean squared error (MMSE) operation, that minimizes data-transfers between the shared-L1 and the upper layers of the memory hierarchy.

A. PUSCH Processing Steps

A 5G uplink transmission is organized in 10 ms-frames, each containing 10 equal subframes. The subframe represented on top of Figure 4 contains OFDM symbols, carrying information sent from UEs to the BS using Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM). 14 OFDM symbols form a Transition Time Interval (TTI). The scalable subcarrier spacing (from 15 kHz to 960 kHz) determines the TTI duration (from 1 ms to 0.015 ms). In this work we consider $\Delta f_{SC} = 15$ kHz subcarrier spacing (1 ms per TTI) and $N_{SC} = 3276$ active subcarriers per OFDM symbol [39]. This results in the time-frequency grid on the top of Figure 4.

The OFDM-symbols are received by N_{RX} antennas. The OFDM-symbol processing at the gNB is detailed in Figure 4. In our analysis PUSCH carries data symbols and demodulation&reference symbols (DMRSs), the latter used to estimate the propagation channel. On the data symbols processing, we first encounter OFDM demodulation, consisting of a per-antenna fast Fourier transform (FFT). Second, beamforming (BF): antenna signals are linearly combined, generating N_B beams, pointing to a specific transmitter. The key operator

Fig. 4. Time-frequency grid of the samples received by the BS in a PUSCH TTI. The data processing for each symbol and the data dependencies between the processing steps and symbols are highlighted in the dependency graph.

```

# fixed-point complex-MAC
pv.shuffle2.h a3, a2, s3
pv.xor.h a4, a2, s4
pv.add.h a4, a4, s5
pv.sdotp.h s1, a3, a1
pv.sdotp.h s2, a4, a1
sra1 s1, 0xf
sra1 s2, 0xf
pv.pack s1, s1, s2

# f16-wDotp complex-MAC
pv.shuffle2.h a3, a2, s3
xor a4, a2, s4
vfdotpex.s.h s1, a3, a1
vfdotpex.s.h s2, a4, a1
vfcпка.h.s s1, s1, s2

# f16-CDotp complex-MAC
fcdotpex.h s1, a1, a2

RISCV32IMA
Xpulpimg
wDotp

```

Fig. 5. Assembly code for complex MAC in different arithmetic precisions.

in BF is a matrix-matrix multiplication (MMM) between the antenna streams and known coefficients. Third, an MMSE detector is applied for each subcarrier. In MIMO systems, N_{TX} UEs transmit on the same subcarrier. Each overlapping UE per subcarrier is a *layer*. The MMSE detector reconstructs the signal of each layer, minimizing the mean squared error between the transmitted and the reconstructed signal.

Indicating with k the subcarrier index, s the symbol index, $y_{k,s}$ the N_B -long received symbol vector, $\hat{x}_{k,s}$ the N_{TX} -long reconstructed symbol, $\hat{H}_{k,s}$ the $N_B \times N_{TX}$ estimated channel coefficient matrix, $\hat{H}_{k,s}^H$ its Hermitian, $\sigma_{k,s}^2$ the channel noise variance and I the identity matrix, the MMSE equation is:

$$\hat{x}_{k,s} = (\hat{H}_{k,s}^H \hat{H}_{k,s} + \sigma_{k,s}^2 I)^{-1} \hat{H}_{k,s}^H y_{k,s} \quad (1)$$

The MMSE operator requires a matrix inversion. Given $G = (\hat{H}_{k,s}^H \hat{H}_{k,s} + \sigma_{k,s}^2 I)$ and $b = \hat{H}_{k,s}^H y_{k,s}$ from Equation (1), we decompose $G = L^H L$ in its lower and upper triangular components, using Cholesky algorithm. The linear system $G\hat{x} = b$ can then be solved by inverting two lower triangular matrices $\hat{x} = L^{-1} ((L^H)^{-1} b)$ [36].

Since the transmission channel is not known a-priori to the receiver, $\hat{H}_{k,s}$ used in the formula is the result of the channel estimation (CHE) procedure that runs over the 2 DMRSs in a TTI, with index $s = 0/1$. The data $x_{k,s}^p$ transmitted for DMRS are *pilots* known both at the transmitter and the receiver, which, given the received signal $y_{k,s}^p$, can therefore be used to estimate the channel through a classical least square estimation (LSE) for the reference signals:

$$\hat{h}_{ij,k,s} = \frac{y_{i,k,s}^p}{x_{j,k,s}^p}, \forall i \in [1, N_B], \forall j \in [1, N_{TX}] \quad (2)$$

Figure 4 highlights the data dependencies between the PUSCH processing steps. In this regard, DMRS0/1 processing, in green, represents a critical block, as its output feeds the MMSE processing for the data symbols.

While the number of subcarriers can be selected to identify a high-load use case according to specifications, the number of antennas, beams, and layers are vendor-specific parameters. 6G requirements will push towards up to 128 antennas and up to 24 layers. Also, not all the slots in a frame are allocated to PUSCH. Therefore, the following decoding operations for the PUSCH symbol can stretch over the slot of other channels, while 1 ms remains a hard limit for OFDM computations, which are paced by the adopted TTI.

B. Software-defined PUSCH Operators Implementation

We implement FP and 16b fixed-point operators for 5G-PUSCH. Inputs and outputs are complex (16b-real and 16b-imaginary). We describe the differences between implementations through the listings in Figure 5, that report the assembly for a complex multiply&accumulate (MAC) implemented with different integer and FP ISA extensions, as an example. The `pv.shuffle.h`, `pv.pack`, and `vfdotpex.s.h` instructions do half-word shuffling and packing of 16b types in 32b types. The `pv.sdotp.h` and `vfdotpex.s.h` implement integer and FP w-Dotp of packed 16b-SIMD types to 32b types. The fixed-point MAC always requires more instructions and registers than FP: an arithmetic shift normalizes the result to fixed-point precision for each integer MAC. The `fcdotpex.h` is the most concise instruction, encoding the four MACs required by the complex w-Dotp.

In our shared-memory cluster, the addresses of L1 follow word-level interleaving: they run contiguously over the 1st to the last Tile TCDM 1st row, then switch to the 2nd memory row. The implementation of PUSCH operators accounts for this: it profits from a fully-shared addressing space, minimizing the cores' conflict to shared memory resources, and reducing unnecessary out-of-Tile memory accesses.

The FFT implementation follows Cooley-Turkey decimation in frequency, a multi-stage algorithm. In the butterfly stages of Figure 6, input quartets produce output quartets (identified by the same color). The butterfly nodes are independent and we assign them to different cores for parallel processing. As shown in the top-right of Figure 6, we store the input quartets in the local memory of the assigned processor, on different memory rows: they can be fetched with minimum latency. Outputs are stored to be fetched with minimum latency by the

next FFT stage. With this approach, an FFT of N complex samples lies on $N/4$ banks and is processed by $N/16$ cores.

Fig. 6. Two butterfly stages of FFT, butterfly nodes are assigned to different cores. Inputs-outputs of a node have the same color. Top-right: cores fetch from local banks, and store inputs for the next stage. Bottom: parallelization of independent FFTs from different antennas.

Fig. 7. MMM parallelization. Cores are assigned the nearest copy of A in the addressing scheme and different columns of C .

To fully utilize the cluster when $N/16 < 1024$, we assign inputs from different antennas to different core groups. For example, at the bottom-right of Figure 6 we execute four independent FFTs of 4096 points in parallel on groups of 256 cores. We separately synchronize cores working on independent FFTs with partial barriers. Synchronization is required after each butterfly stage. To reduce the overhead we let the cores work on the same stage of independent FFTs from different antennas in time sequence before the barrier.

BF is a 3-loop complex MMM $C = A \times B$: matrix A is a known $N_B \times N_{RX}$ coefficient matrix, B is the $N_{RX} \times N_{SC}$ output of OFDM. Parallelization is over the columns of B , on the subcarriers dimension. To maximize the compute intensity of the kernel, the loops are unrolled. Therefore, a single-core crosses multiple columns of A and B , to produce an output tile in C . In the inner loop, all the inputs and partial sums must fit in the RF, and the tile must be as big as possible, to maximize data reuse. A 2×4 output tile minimizes the variables pushed

to the stack in the inner loop of the fixed-point and FP w-Dotp implementation. We use 16 registers for the real and imaginary parts of the accumulators, 4 registers for A inputs, and 8 for B inputs. In the complex-w-Dotp FP implementation, an output element is computed in a single Snitch instruction offload. This reduces the number of partial sum registers used. As a result, the output computation window grows to 4×4 . Data in the inner loop is never pushed to the stack: we use 8 registers for inputs, 16 to accumulate temporary results, 3 for address increment, and 3 for loop control.

In our use case A , the $N_B \times N_{RX}$ BF coefficient matrix, and B , the $N_{RX} \times N_{SC}$ data matrix from OFDM are unbalanced in size. Figure 7 shows how we distribute the data for this application in memory. Given the parallelization scheme, matrix B is aligned to memory boundaries, reducing accesses outside a Tile. All the cores fetch elements in matrix A . To reduce the resulting congestion in the interconnect we adopt two solutions. First, we align matrix A to the memory rows and create multiple copies to fill up one row of the cluster's memory (in Figure 7 we represent the case for $N_B \times N_{RX} = 32 \times 64$, resulting in two copies of A). When different beams apply to different groups of subcarriers, matrices with different coefficients can also be used, instead of A copies. We then assign to each core the matrix A copy that is closer in the cluster addressing scheme. Second, we assign cores in the same Tile a different starting point in the loop across rows of A . This way it is less likely that cores will conflict for the same Tile port during out-of-Tile accesses. The bottom part of Figure 7 represents different iterations of matrix C computation: the cores start iterating from different rows of C and go back to the first row, once they complete a column.

CHE produces N_{SC} matrices of size $N_B \times N_{TX}$, from N_{SC} array couples of size N_{TX} and N_B . Since the receiver holds prior knowledge of the DMRS transmission, we assume that the kernel is fed the reciprocal of $x^p_{j,k,s}$ values in Equation (2). In the parallelization, each core is assigned the generation of the channel estimate for a different subcarrier.

From Equation (1), the MMSE operator requires the implementation of the channel Hermitian, the matrix-vector multiplication (MVM) between the channel complex-conjugate and the received symbol, the Cholesky decomposition, and the solution of a triangular system. We implement these kernels for a single Snitch: the MMSE problem has strong inner data dependencies, harnessing efficient parallelization. Yet, the size of the inverted matrix depends on the N_{TX} , ranging between 4 and 32, while N_{SC} can be thousands, suggesting that the best choice is a coarse-grained parallelization of independent MMSE problems over the large dimensional subcarriers space.

C. PUSCH Operators Performance Analysis

Figure 8 represents the cycle-count of the implemented kernels measured in RTL cycle-accurate simulation of the cluster (Questasim 2022.3). We change the input size over the parallelization dimension of each kernel. For FFT and BF, we set $N_B = 32$ and $N_{SC} = 4096$, and vary N_{RX} , for CHE and MMSE we set $N_B = 32$ and $N_{TX} = 4$, and vary N_{SC} . We mark the fixed-point and the FP implementations

Fig. 8. Compute cycles of the implemented FP and fixed-point kernels for different numbers of receiver antennas, subcarriers, beams, and layers. The skewed bars represent the arrival times of the first and last core to synchronization, the gray part represents synchronization and work-imbalance overheads.

Fig. 9. BER vs SNR of MMSE for different sizes and arithmetic precisions.

with $q16$ and $f16$. The most time-consuming processing step is BF (80 Kcycles/symbol in $q16$ and 62 Kcycles/symbol in FP). Using `fcdotpex.h` ($cf16$) we spare registers and instructions, reporting up to $3.8\times$ speedup, compared to the cycle-count of FP-BF with w -Dotp extensions only. The FP processing is bottlenecked by the FFT (40 Kcycles per symbol). CHE is a small overhead: less than 10 Kcycles, only required for DMRS symbols. The skewed bars mark the arrival time of the first and last core to the barrier, clarifying how synchronization affects the runtime.

In Figure 9, we also compare the arithmetic precision of the $f16$ against $q16$, reporting the uncoded BER of the MMSE, assuming a 16QAM modulation and transmission through additive white Gaussian noise channel. As expected [33], the BER of $q16$ is higher than $f16$ and degrades on large problems.

In Figure 10 we break down the average core instruction issues and architectural stalls over the total cycles, for each input dimension, and precision. Instruction stalls refer to cache misses, RAW stalls to cores waiting for data from the external pipelined and shared functional units or the memory interface. If the LSU transaction table is full, the LSU stalls to the processor. The external functional units can also stall Snitch if their pipelines are busy. The WFI stalls are encountered in synchronization when cores wait at the barrier for others to complete their job. The plots highlight LSU stalls and RAW stalls as the main source of work imbalance. The $f16$ -BF for

$N_{RX} = 64$ is an example: as replication of matrix A on the first memory row of interleaved banks is limited to two 32×64 replicas, LSU stalls and work imbalance increase. For CHE and MMSE, the subcarrier-wise parallelization forces out-of-Tile accesses to data interleaved across all the banks. In turn, this increases LSU stalls. We also observe more RAW stalls, caused by two main factors. First, in the subcarrier-wise parallelization, the loops are smaller. Data reuse is limited and more loads are required. This creates pressure on the interconnect and limits the throughput to the cores, now more often waiting for data. Second, in MMSE the cores must queue for division and square-roots executed in the shared unit.

Nevertheless, working on large data chunks reduces synchronization overheads and increases the IPC. An example is the FFT, which also benefits from the peculiar synchronization strategy: we compute a stage of the Cooley-Turkey algorithm for all the antennas and then synchronize. On average we achieve 0.8-0.68 IPC (FP and fixed-point) on the per-antenna FFT and BF parallelization, which takes most of the time in a TTI. We obtain 0.6-0.48 IPC on the more challenging CHE and MMSE per-subcarrier parallelization. Considering the IPC of the entire processing pipeline for the maximum dimensions under exam, the overall average IPC is 0.75-0.61.

To evaluate the effect of the hierarchical interconnect scale-up on parallelization, we run the kernels on a SubGroup/Group with respectively 64/256-cores and 1 MiB/256 KiB memory. We scale the input size over the parallelization dimension by the core-count ratio, ensuring that the workload fits in the SubGroup/Group memory, and Snitch executes the same number of instructions as in the full 1024-core cluster. Figure 11 shows the ratio between the operators' runtime on the full cluster and the SubGroup/Group. For BF and MMSE, memory accesses spread over all the banks, and the full cluster performs better than the SubGroup: cores in a Tile will access different request-response ports, instead of competing for the same. The full cluster is at maximum 40% (CHE) slower than a Group. On average we measured 22% slow-down, mainly caused by synchronization stalls, demonstrating a tolerable effect of the cluster hierarchical scale-up on parallelization.

Fig. 10. IPC and architectural stalls breakdown of the implemented $q16$ and $f16$ kernels for different numbers of antennas, subcarriers, beams, and layers.

Fig. 11. Ratio between the runtime of the full cluster and a SubGroup/Group on the implemented kernels. We consider both a SubGroup/Group with the same core-to-memory interconnect of TeraPool and an all-to-all fully connected SubGroup/Group. Input size is scaled over the parallelization dimension.

We also consider an all-to-all fully connected SubGroup/Group. In this case, each core in a Tile has a memory request-response port to a 1 cycle latency 64×64 or 256×256 X-BAR. Assuming these ideal yet physically unfeasible cluster configurations, our 1024-core shared-memory cluster obtains 35%/26% average performance loss, compared to a SubGroup/Group. However, the biggest loss (up to 46% and 57%) is reported for CHE, which requires less cycles than other benchmarks and does not influence the full chain performance.

Scaling up the shared memory hierarchically enables a physically feasible interconnect [19], [37]. Contentions for interconnect resources, bank conflicts, and synchronization overheads increase compared with the ideal all-to-all cluster. However, computing the same workload over smaller parallel clusters with private TCDMs requires many copies of the shared data and forces solving data-dependencies between kernels executed on different clusters using producer-consumer queues and synchronizing across the clusters' hierarchies. This leads to data transfer overheads and increased program complexity. Multi-cluster parallelization is not desirable for PUSCH, a large but rather uniform workload over the antennas (OFDM) and the subcarriers (MMSE) dimensions, which can be easily parallelized on a single cluster.

D. PUSCH Operators Scheduling

Alongside the processing pipeline building blocks, we also implemented full 5G applications, namely the sequence of OFDM and BF, and MIMO-MMSE detection. Combining the kernels for these applications, we consider the overhead of data movement, from the L1 scratchpad to the upper memory hierarchies, and we try to minimize them.

BF combines the OFDM antenna data streams to generate beam data streams. It must collect the output of N_{RX} FFTs. The cluster L1 memory is large enough to fit the data for up to 64 antennas and can be used as a computing buffer. By stitching OFDM and BF, so that the data from FFT flows directly to the MMM we avoid resorting to L2 transfers. When the BF conditions do not change, executing multiple OFDM symbols in sequence leads to the further advantage of keeping the coefficients matrix for BF in L1. We pay once the transfer from L2 and the replica of coefficients to the local memory of the cluster cores. Similarly, the output of CHE is kept in L1, to compute MMSE on adjacent symbols.

The benefit is demonstrated in Figure 12, where we propose different strategies to transfer data for the computation of OFDM and MMSE symbols. We try two approaches. In the first, the last core at the synchronization barrier transfers computed data and inputs for the next symbol. In the second, we instantiate a compute and a transfer buffer in memory.

Fig. 12. Execution cycles for an OFDM and a MMSE symbol under different transfer options for inputs and outputs. The skewed bars represent the arrival of the first and last core to the synchronization barrier.

Fig. 13. Proposed execution pipeline for 7 symbols, in a system with $N_{RX} = 64$, $N_B = 32$, $N_{SC} = 4096$, $N_{TX} = 4$ layers per subcarrier. L1 data shared over different computation steps is marked by dashed arrows.

While computing, we transfer the data for the next symbol in the transfer buffer, using the DMA. During synchronization, we also wait for the DMA. The first bar in each plot of Figure 12 follows the first transfer method. It considers the transfer overhead of moving the BF coefficients and the channel matrix from L2 at each symbol. In the case of OFDM we also include the transfer of the FFT results to memory. Experiments with results reported in the second bars also follow the first transfer method. Using the large L1 as a compute buffer we reduce the total runtime of 6% for OFDM and of 11% for MMSE. In the case of OFDM we also benefit from directly pipelining FFT and BF in L1. The third bar shows the results for the second transfer method. The overlap between computation and asynchronous transfer by DMA engine is reported. During asynchronous transfers the DMA can conflict with cores for the scratchpad banks, affecting the runtime. For this reason, we start the MMSE transfers after the computation of the hermitian matrix, which requires heavy memory access. Double buffering gives an additional 6% runtime improvement in OFDM.

Finally, we propose the pipeline to execute a full PUSCH TTI. We assume a gNB system with $N_{RX} = 64$, $N_B = 32$,

$N_{SC} = 4096$, and $\Delta f_{SC} = 15$ kHz. We consider $N_{TX} = 4$ UEs transmitting on each subcarrier, to test the processing chain under full load hypothesis. The execution pipeline for 7 TTI symbols is in Figure 13, and it repeats for the next 7 symbols. Each replica of the cluster refers to a different computation step over time. The L1 data shared over multiple time steps is marked by dotted arrows, data transfers are represented by solid arrows. L1 memory is used as a low-latency buffer for the FFT output, feeding BF, and the channel estimate, feeding MMSE over multiple symbols.

IV. PHYSICAL IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

In this section, we report the performance and area of our design, and the results of power simulations for key NR kernels, running on the cluster. We then combine these data with execution time to perform an end-to-end performance and energy efficiency analysis for a PUSCH TTI computation.

A. Physical Implementation

The physical feasibility of a baseline TeraPool was demonstrated in [19]. In this work, we challenged the implementation of the TeraPool cluster with Zfinx extensions and complex w-Dotp in GlobalFoundries' 12 nm LPPLUS FinFET technology. We use Synopsys' Fusion Compiler 2022.03 for synthesis and place&route (PnR). The Post-PnR peak-performance & area of our cluster, including FP support are reported in Table I.

TABLE I
POST-PNR PEAK-PERFORMANCE & AREA RESULTS.

	TeraPool	This work
Cluster Area [mm ²]	68.9	81.8
SubGroup Area [mm ²]	2.30	3.01
Area Per Core [mm ² /core]	0.067	0.080
Logic Gate Per Core [MGE/core]	0.17	0.22
Operating Frequency (<i>Worst</i>) [MHz]	637	634
Operating Frequency (<i>Typ.</i>) [MHz]	880	875
Peak Performance (<i>Typ.</i>) [TFLOPS]	1.80	1.79
Peak Performance (<i>Typ.</i>) [Complex – TFLOPS]	/	1.79

Adding FP support to the core complex improves the numerical precision of detection algorithms. Programming is also easier, as there is no need to rescale the representation range, depending on algorithms and operating conditions. The additional area cost is acceptable. The FP unit is a significant overhead (+40%) on the core-complex area. On the Tile level, however, the area is 20% of the total, and on the cluster level, it corresponds to an overhead of only 18%. The routing channels introduced in the top-level of TeraPool by [19] do not change in size, resulting in no area waste for the cluster PnR. Finally, the shared division and square-root units represent only 2% of the Tile area, reducing the cost of these extensions, which would, on the contrary, be too expensive if added to the core (an additional estimated 20%).

The design does not incur operating frequency penalties compared to the cluster with cores only supporting integer instructions. It runs at 634 MHz in the worst corner (125°C, 0.88 V), and at 875 MHz in the typical corner (25°C, 0.8 V). At this frequency, the peak performance is 1.79 TOPS, and

the L2 memory bandwidth (7.2Tbps) can sustain the raw in-phase and quadrature (IQ) data-rate per antenna ($N_{RX} \times IQ_{bits} \times N_{SC} \times \Delta f_{SC} = 126Gbps$ in the target use-case with $IQ_{bits} = 16b + 16b$). Figure 14 represents a snapshot of the SubGroup instance and the Tile. The FPU's, the IPU's, the Snitch cores, the shared division and square-root units, the IS, and the X-BARs are highlighted.

Fig. 14. Snapshot of the SubGroup instance and zoom over a Tile, highlighting the FPU's, the IPU's, the Snitch cores, the division and square-root units, the IS, and the X-BARs.

Fig. 15. Breakdown over the hierarchies of the cluster of the power consumed to run a TTI. In *others* we include the power of backend optimization cells and cells flattened by synthesis for timing optimization.

Fig. 16. Breakdown of execution time and energy consumption over processing steps, for the PUSCH computations in a TTI.

B. Throughput & Power Simulations

Table II reports the performance of the cluster on the kernels of PUSCH. We consider an instance running in the typical corner (25°C, 0.8 V, at 800 MHz), and the high load use case with $N_{SC} = 4096$, $N_{RX} = 64$, $N_B = 32$, $N_{TX} = 4$. We compute the throughput metric depending on the processing step runtime, for a fair comparison with the SoTA. For FFT and BF (agnostic of N_{TX}) we consider the IQ antenna throughput:

$$\frac{N_{RX} \times IQ_{bits} \times N_{SC}}{\#cycles} \times f_{ck}, \quad IQ_{bits} = (16b + 16b) \quad (3)$$

CHE, and MMSE, are agnostic of N_{RX} . We consider the raw IQ symbol throughput replacing N_{RX} with N_{TX} in

Equation (3). Finally, we report the throughput and power consumption for the PUSCH processing in a TTI (Figure 4), executed as in Figure 13. We divide the antenna bits ($N_{RX} \times IQ_{bits} \times N_{SC} \times 14$) by the runtime measured in RTL simulation (Questasim 2022.3). Power is extracted from post-layout simulations using Synopsys PrimeTime 2022-03.

The uplink achieves 44 Gbps/5.9W for the *q16* implementation (BF is the bottleneck), and 66.3 Gbps/5.54W for the FP processing chain. Figure 15 represents the breakdown of the main architectural components' power consumption across the cluster hierarchies. The Snitch cores and the functional units represent the main contribution to power consumption (40%-43%, fixed-floating). Accesses to scratchpad memories and the IS contribute 0.18%-0.12%. Finally, interconnections, including AXI, DMA, and TCDM hierarchical X-BARs, contribute only 7.7%-8.7%. This result highlights the energy efficiency of our hierarchical design.

We estimate a total latency of 2.6 ms (*q16*) and 1.7 ms (*f16*). Running a TTI as in Figure 12 results in 60-100 Gbps per OFDM and 7.7-8.8 Gbps per MMSE (*q16-f16*). Figure 16 shows the energy and time spent in each processing step for a TTI. The breakdown shows that for both the *f16* and *q16* implementations, most of the energy&time is consumed by OFDM. Running separately OFDM and MMSE&CHE on two clusters, PUSCH TTI throughput would be limited by the OFDM stage, requiring 1.96 ms in *q16* and 1.17 ms in *f16*. The total average power consumption for the two clusters is 11.8 W (*q16*) and 11.1 W (*f16*).

V. RELATED WORKS

This section compares our cluster with SoTA solutions for gNB processing. We group and compare the processing engines for 5G-NR from academic literature in three main categories, based on their programmability (Table I). Under general purpose processor (GPP) [40], we report DSP solutions based on programmable processors, supporting a full ISA. These are the most flexible in programmability and the best candidates to pursue software-defined wireless processing.

In the ASIP category we report programmable devices, with a reduced custom ISA tailored to the gNB workload [41]–[46]. Compared to GPPs, they target higher frequencies at lower power consumption, but they require architecture specialization. As a result ASIPs will execute a limited number of workloads, with fixed problem sizes. The very-large instruction word (VLIW) architecture chosen by [43] and [44] to maximize task specialization also adds complexity to the programming model, exacerbating the issue. This is not optimal for software-defined gNB processing, considering the fast-paced evolution of telecommunication standards, input data dimensions, and algorithms.

The ASIC category includes accelerators tailored to specific workloads, targeting high performance, with extreme architecture specialization [20]–[24]. These engines have limited reconfigurability options and can be used to accelerate gNB workloads in heterogeneous systems, with programmable cores handling data movement and control operations.

Our solution is a cluster of ISA-enhanced RISC-V cores. Its position in the SoTA, compared to ASIPs and ASICs is

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF SOTA HARDWARE FOR LOWER-PHY 5G BASE STATION PROCESSING

Technology	Area [mm ²]	Frequency	Kernel	*† Throughput [Gbps]	*Power [W]	*Energy-Eff. [Gbps/W]	*Energy&Area-Eff. [Gbps/W/mm ²]	
This Work	GPP (GF-12nm)	81.8	800 MHz	FFT q16 (64x4096)	204.59	6.09	33.58	0.41
				FFT f16 (64x4096)	150.38	5.63	26.70	0.33
				BF q16 (32x64x4096)	84.40	6.28	13.44	0.16
				BF cf16 (32x64x4096)	302.30	7.22	41.85	0.51
				CHE q16 (32x4x4096)	43.59	5.40	8.07	0.10
				CHE f16 (32x4x4096)	45.67	4.56	10.02	0.12
				MMSE q16 (16QAM 4x4x4096)	9.36	4.95	1.89	0.02
				MMSE f16 (16QAM 4x4x4096)	10.87	4.34	2.50	0.03
				FFT&BF q16	59.75	6.23	9.60	0.12
				FFT&BF f16	100.43	6.16	16.30	0.20
				CHE&MMSE q16	7.71	5.03	1.53	0.02
				CHE&MMSE f16	8.78	4.38	2.00	0.02
				PUSCH TTI q16	44.12	5.90	7.48	0.09
PUSCH TTI f16	66.3	5.54	11.96	0.14				
Amor [40]	GPP (GF-22nm <i>synth.</i>)	0.0081	100 MHz	FSK	0.15	1.94	0.08	31.50
				LoRa	0.19	1.96	0.10	41.18
Chen [41]	ASIP (65nm)	1.4	400 MHz	MMSE (64QAM 32x64)	12.86	0.02	544.20	11405.02
Kultala [42]	ASIP (TSMC-28nm)	2.5	968 MHz	LORD (2x2)	4.62	0.09	49.15	66.88
				MMSE (64QAM, 4x4)	6.25	0.09	66.54	90.54
Fu [43]	ASIP (TSMC-28nm)	4.35	500 MHz	FFT (2048)	52.73	0.05	1106.42	1384.79
				MMSE (256QAM, 128x8)	15.03	0.04	335.93	420.45
Attari [44]	ASIP (TSMC-28nm)	0.97	800 MHz	ZF (64QAM, 128x8)	6.75	0.09	79.25	272.92
				MMSE (64QAM, 128x8)	3.58	0.09	42.04	144.77
Castaneda [45]	ASIP (GF-22nm)	0.42	293 MHz	MMSE (256QAM 128x16)	1.76	0.05	33.26	90.17
Chen [46]	ASIP (TSMC-28nm)	10.3	800 MHz	FFT	7.31	1.25	5.83	3.08
				CHE	7.31	1.25	5.83	3.08
				MIMO (16QAM 2x2)	7.31	1.25	5.83	3.08
Peng [20]	ASIC (28nm)	2.57	680 MHz	MMSE (64QAM 128x8)	29.47	0.08	383.68	4380.27
Tang [21]	ASIC (40nm)	0.58	425 MHz	MPD (256QAM 128x32)	27.60	0.05	529.26	10139.11
Shahabuddin [22]	ASIC (TSMC-65nm)	0.69	606 MHz	ADMIN (64QAM 64x32)	4.79	0.04	129.31	1023.25
Guo [23]	ASIC (TSMC-12nm)	0.75	1 GHz	FFT (4096)	99.20	0.78	127.48	169.97
Yang [24]	ASIC (SMIC-40nm <i>synth.</i>)	0.84	483 MHz	FFT (2048)	69.76	-	-	-
Zhang [25]	ASIC (40nm)	4.36	200 MHz	BP (16QAM 8x8)	32.77	0.07	452.85	1154.04

*Throughput, power, and area were normalized to GlobalFoundries' 12nm LPPLUS FinFET technology, multiplying respectively by the feature size ratio s , $\frac{1}{s}(\frac{0.8V_s}{V_{DD}})^2$, $\frac{1}{s^2}$.

†Raw IQ-data throughput. The results for ASIPs and ASICs are computed according to adopted data-width and modulation scheme.

TABLE III
INDUSTRY SOCs FOR LOWER-PHY 5G BASE STATION PROCESSING

Platform	PHY processors	ISA	Multi-core	SW-defined operators	5G-split
NVIDIA AX800 [47]	Ampere GPU BlueField-3 DPU	NVIDIA	yes (8192c)	cuMAC cuPHY	8
EdgeQ/S-series [26]	TXU processor ARM Neoverse-E1	RISC-V ARM	yes (60c) yes (8c)	Demodulation Beamforming 64x64 MIMO Matrix decomposition Channel Estimation Equalization	6-7.2
Picocom/PC802 [27]	Ceva XC12 1280-bit Scalar-processors cluster	RISC-V RISC-V	no yes (25c)	Digital Front-End Encoding-Decoding Demodulation 4x8 MIMO	7.2X
Marvell/Octeon10-CNF105xx [28]	ARM Neoverse-N2 DSP processors Accelerators	ARM n.a.	yes (<36c) yes	64x64 MIMO Others (n.a.)	7.X
Qualcomm/X100 [29]	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	Demodulation Beamforming 64x64 MIMO Channel Coding	7.X
Platform	PHY processors	HW-defined operator		5G-split	
Xilinx/Zynq-Ultrascale&RFSoc [48]	Programmable Logic ARM Cortex-A53 (4c) Accelerators	Demodulation PRACH		7.X	

clarified in Figure 17, where the focus is on energy efficiency. To allow a fair comparison, the throughput, power, and area of the proposed SoTA solutions were normalized to GlobalFoundries’ 12 nm LPPLUS FinFET technology³. Our many-core has 1024 cores running at high frequency, thanks to an aggressive backend design in an advanced technology node. Its FFT-throughput largely outperforms the SoTA single-core GPP solution ($> 1000\times$ on a similar workload). TeraPool achieves up to $6.2\times$ (MMSE), and $28\times$ (FFT), higher throughput than ASIPs, and up to $2\times$ higher FFT-throughput than the ASICs in our survey. Differently from the SoTA ASIPs and ASICs, the programmable TeraPool cores support a full uplink workload. Its 66.3Gbps TTI-throughput fulfills the 5G 20Gbps uplink requirement and follows the increasing rates of 6G workloads [6], [8]. The penalty is higher power consumption. The programmable cluster requires up to $100\times$ more average power than specialized datapaths to execute 6G kernels. In Figure 17 we report the throughput provided by a SubGroup versus its power consumption in kernels execution.

In comparing energy efficiency with ASIPs and ASICs, it is important to note that all published results target a much lower throughput and are measured on only a subset of a functionally complete PUSH workload. Clearly, the functional flexibility and high throughput of our cluster have a price in area and energy efficiency. To put this statement in perspective, let’s consider [42], which has 128 complex MAC units, the highest in our survey. A SubGroup (64 cores) achieves similar energy and area efficiency. The area efficiency reduction resulting from the scaling up of our cluster to match beyond 5G and 6G requirements is mainly caused by the top-level routing channels, as highlighted by [19]. However, a bigger shared-memory cluster offers two main advantages. First, the large L1 can entirely accommodate the data footprint of a PUSCH workload. As demonstrated, it can be used as compute buffer, to hide transfer latencies. It also simplifies the programming model: we benefit from massive SPMD, with no need for data transfers and synchronization between many small clusters. Second, the cluster is more versatile than extremely specialized programmable solutions, such as [43] and [44], resulting in a better match for software-defined lower-PHY workloads.

Finally, considering 10 W power budget per BS DSP component [17], [18], our scaled-up solution matches the required power consumption and exceeds by $6\times$ the energy efficiency constraints (2 Gbps/W). We observe that energy efficiency is constant if we consider the scaling of one SubGroup to the full cluster, for minimal energy overhead of interconnections.

We also compare our approach to rapidly evolving industry solutions for software-defined 5G processing. Relevant examples are reported in Table III. general-purpose graphic processing units (GP-GPUs) achieve high-performance parallelization and keep software versatility. They are nowadays the main computing platforms for deep-learning applications, and they are also considered good options to fill the flexibility/performance gap required by 5G and beyond [49]. In fact, aiming for the reuse of existing GP-GPU cloud infrastructure in the

Fig. 17. Comparison of the energy efficiency of our cluster with ASIC and ASIP SoTA solutions for gNB processing. The star represents the results for one PUSCH symbol.

domain of 5G, NVIDIA fostered RAN virtualization [50]. Wireless processing software libraries [51], [52] with CUDA support were developed to run on commodity cloud hardware, such as the AX800 converged accelerator [47], which achieves 36.56 Gbps (downlink) and 4.79 Gbps (uplink) throughput. The performance of GP-GPUs on wireless workloads was also revealed by academic research: [49] achieves 3.96 Gbps on LDPC decoding, previous works on older GP-GPUs generations report 0.13-0.52 Gbps on parallel decoding of many independent MIMO systems [53], [54]. An analysis of the power consumption of these platforms on 5G benchmarks is however still not disclosed in the open literature. With 350 W peak power consumption, AX800 usage is recommended in a cloud infrastructure [47]. GP-GPU based RAN processing, therefore targets 5G split 8 [9], where none of the PHY functions is implemented in the BS, putting high requirements on the data rates of the network fronthaul: 100 Gbps [50].

The field programmable gate array (FPGA) solutions [48] accelerate the computationally intensive uplink operations on the programmable logic, while data transfers and control are executed on a multi-core central processing unit (CPU). Despite lower time-to-market than ASICs, adapting the gNB to programmable logic requires more implementation and verification effort, compared to a streamlined software approach.

[26]–[28] are heterogeneous platforms all containing one or more programmable components. They implement the 5G split 7.X, where the PHY functions up to decoding of the received signals are offloaded to the BS [9]. For all these platforms, vendors offer pre-built libraries of kernels with the hardware.

Our approach is aligned with this trend: it can be used to implement a software defined version of split 7.X and it offers additional advantages. First, it has at least $10\times$ more cores than all the clusters used in industry platforms for deployment at the network’s edge. Its processing elements are however smaller and architecturally simple. The core complex occupies only 80 kGE and a SubGroup instance, including 64 cores and 1 MiB of memory occupies 2.3 mm^2 in 12 nm. The ARM Neoverse-N2 in [28] is more bulky: a single core occupies 1.3 mm^2 [55] in 5 nm. Second, it offers competitive power consumption. It consumes 5.54 W on average for PUSCH uplink. This processing is similar to the downlink workload described by [29], which in turn consumes

³Throughput, power, and area where normalized multiplying respectively by the feature size ratio s , $\frac{1}{s}(\frac{0.8V}{\sqrt{DD}})^2$, $\frac{1}{s^2}$

~ 18 W on the X100 card. Third, it proposes an efficient novel shared-memory architecture. This work showed how this can be used to implement an in-line processing pipeline, where the L1 memory is used as a low-latency compute buffer.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper addressed the three main problems arising from the scale-up of beyond 5G transmission bandwidth and number of subcarriers: throughput, energy efficiency, and lifetime of BS hardware components. The proposed solution is a many-core cluster of 1024 lightweight RISC-V processing elements, sharing 4 MiB of L1 memory. The high core count pushes peak performance on key NR kernels to 20 Gbps, beyond 5G requirements. We estimate average power consumption of < 6 W and a total latency of 2.6 ms ($q16$) and 1.7 ms ($f16$) for the execution of PUSCH. The big shared memory reduces expensive transfers of large NR data, maximizing the computing phases of processing. Scaling up the shared-memory cluster, using hierarchical X-BAR interconnects keeps energy efficiency high. Our design achieves 9.4-300 Gbps/W on all the kernels under test, up to $28\times$ larger than other ASIPs in the SoTA. It executes a PUSCH symbol at 12 Gbps/W. Finally, the programmable RISC-V Snitch core and the cluster' streamlined programming model enable a full software-defined processing approach, a key asset to keep up with evolving telecommunication standards.

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